

REPRESENTATION OF THE CONCEPT OF PROMISE IN THE SPEECH OF DEPUTIES

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Abstract. This article discusses the concept and its linguodidactics, the concept of “promise” about its uniqueness and its expression in speech by linguists and subjective attitude to the scientific views of pedagogues.

Key words: Speech by deputies, concept, promise, linguocultural concept.

ПРЕДСТАВЛЕНИЕ ПОНЯТИЯ ОБЕЩАНИЯ В РЕЧИ ДЕПУТАТОВ

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматривается концепт и его лингводидактика, понятие “обещание” о его уникальности и его выражении в речи лингвистами, а также субъективное отношение к научным взглядам педагогов.

Ключевые слова: выступление депутатов, концепт, обещание, лингвокультурный концепт.

During the following years, Uzbek linguistics developed in our country, is improving. Linguistics in the mutual integration of other disciplines is the role of science is important. Therefore, it is a philosophical concept the word calculated concept is the object of study of linguistics recently is given importance as The concept is full of concepts of the concept of honesty we will try to comment on its definition and clarify its conceptual basis. Concept is a unit of the linguistic and cultural field in modern linguistics, because it is language, reflects knowledge about society and its culture. Concepts in language reflects culture and forms the image of the world in the human mind. Concept operational content unit of thinking, systematized knowledge unit or is a quantum.¹ “Concepts are ideals, abstractions that a person uses in the process of thinking are units, meanings. The knowledge they get is experience, a person's perception of real existence reflects the content of the results in the form of certain units, “quanta”². Various semantic interpretation of the lexicon of concepts into a set of specific units characterized by relatedness.

N.N. Boldirev says that “in language, the concept is separate words and words verbalized by means of combinations, phraseological units, sentences and whole texts it can”³.

It should be said that the concept of “promise” is a linguistic and cultural concept, which is expressed in human thinking and worldview. This linguistic and cultural concept is a universal feeling that has a significant impact on the formation and development of the qualities of nationality and humanity. Expression of the concept of “promise” by means of phraseological units, sentences, whole texts is considered a syntactic unit and a linguistic level that serves to understand its true essence. It is known that there are many concepts that are part of cultural speech and are actively used in speech activity at a certain level. They are distinguished by their presence

¹ Е.С. Кубрякова, В.З. Демьянков, Ю.Г. Панкрац, Л.Г. Лузина. Краткий словарь когнитивных терминов. – Москва, 1997. – Б. 90

² Н.Н. Болдырев. Когнитивная семантика: Курс лекций по английской филологии: учебное пособие. Изд.5-е, стер. – Москва-Берлин: DirectMedia, 2016. – Б. 30.

³ . Н.Н. Болдырев. Когнитивная семантика: Курс лекций по английской филологии: учебное пособие. Изд.5-е, стер. – Москва-Берлин: DirectMedia, 2016. – Б.36-47.

in oral and written speech. One of the concepts with such a conceptual basis is the concept of “promise”. The concept of “promise” is manifested in the important factors that determine the relationship between the speaker and the listener during the speech process.

In the “Explanatory Dictionary of the Uzbek Language” the lexeme “promise” is mentioned as a word for doing or not doing something. In the Uzbek language, the concept of “promise” is expressed in noun and verb combinations such as “promise”, “term”, “to undertake”. It is known that “when creating a speech, a person is not only interested in its topic, but also expresses his feelings during the speech process. Emotions and inner experience in the speech process are formed as a private attitude of a person... a private emotional attitude, of course, originates from the mental state of the author of the text and is understood directly from the content of the text”⁴. The concept of “promise” is one of the internal feelings that “takes the main place in the relationship between two or more participants who have entered into a dialogue. The expressiveness of the use of the concept of “promise” in the speech process is shown as follows:

- creates a sense of trust between people;
- increases the positive indicator of hard work;
- strengthens mutual communication;
- calls to be honest and fair, to acquire strong knowledge;
- expands the process of independent thinking;
- determines the leading topic in communicative qualities that ensure the culture of speech.

Based on the conclusions of the above lexical-semantic analysis, let us pay attention to the practical meaning of the concept of “promise”. In particular, in the speeches of deputies this concept has a negative connotation. In recent years, in the media, especially in the pages of the press, deputies elected to local councils do not fulfill the tasks specified in their election program, and the noble status of a deputy has turned into negative images of “vadaboz” in the public mind.

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⁴ Hakimov M. O`zbek tilida matnning pragmatik talqini: filol. Fan. Doct. Diss. Toshkent. 2001. 34-35-betlar